

THE ESSENCE AND KEY ASPECTS OF THE CONCEPT OF GENDER CULTURE

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Abstract. *The existing inequalities between different layers of society (urban and rural), ethnic origin, age, education, and other categories are based on inequalities between countries and within countries in terms of the level of development. The two largest social groups in humanity are women and men. The differences in human development between these two social groups are the most important, constant, and universal. Equal rights and access to education, active and equal participation in political life, and employment opportunities for women and men remain a global issue. Therefore, measuring gender inequalities in human development and expanding opportunities for women and girls continues to be a priority task worldwide.*

Keywords: *ethnic origin, political life, equal rights, amendments, urban and rural society*

In our country, women make up nearly 50% of the population. They contribute actively and effectively to all areas of social, cultural, political, and economic life. Our main law, the Constitution, acknowledges that women have equal rights in all sectors. In the decisions and decrees issued by the government, the interests of women, families, and children are prioritized.

It is known that, in order to achieve gender equality, large-scale measures are being implemented. On May 28, 2021, the Senate of the Oliy Majlis of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted the Resolution SQ-297-IV, titled "Approval of the Strategy for Achieving Gender Equality by 2030." [1] This Strategy provides for measures aimed at implementing the principles of equality between men and women in all aspects, as well as strengthening the participation and rights of women in public life.

It is known that the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Amendments and Additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men" of 2023 defines the tasks of state bodies in the field of ensuring gender equality and further strengthening the mechanisms for implementing equality. [2] These documents are important for achieving gender equality in the country, protecting women's rights and creating equal opportunities for them.

At this point, we would like to talk about the term "Gender". The term "gender" was first used in a new sense in 1968 by psychoanalyst Robert Stoller in his book "Sex and Gender". Anthony Giddens later explained that the term "gender" does not refer to biological differences between men and women, but to social constructs that determine their behavior and identity [3].

Russian sociologists E. Zdravomyslova and A. Temkina emphasize that gender is a social status that determines individual opportunities in education, professional activity, access to power, sexual relations, family roles and reproductive behavior [4]. From an early age, boys and girls are assigned different gender roles and taught to perform socially prescribed male and female roles. This process is called gender socialization and is aimed at reinforcing the roles of men and women in society.

Gender socialization is supported and reinforced through key tools such as the family, where parents teach their children the roles of “male” and “female”; school, where gender stereotypes are reinforced by teachers and students; public spaces, places that offer toys and clothes for boys and girls; and the media, which broadcast traditional gender norms and stereotypes. Art, language, and culture also play a large role in this process. It is important to remember that gender roles and norms are not constant - they can change over time, adapt to social changes, and be shaped by the cultural context.

The ideas about gender types inherent in a particular society are specific to a particular historical period. Gender stereotypes are formed through the process of socialization, starting in a person’s youth. In this regard, the cultural norms of behavior that have developed in society, cultural relationships between people, customs, and the environment have a special influence. As a result of socialization, skills for mastering certain social roles are formed. At different stages, clothing, verbal addresses, parental demands, toys, folk oral and written literature, radio, television, cinema, school education, and the opinions of peers and classmates act as factors of socialization, information from social networks can be displayed.

Hovsted emphasizes that differences in gender roles are manifested in different cultures through the differentiation of gender roles, which is expressed through the degrees of masculinity and femininity in a particular culture. People in a masculine culture, as a rule, have a high motivation for achievement. They see the meaning of life in working hard and being constantly busy. People belonging to a feminist culture want to be more involved in family life and achieve equality in the roles they play. This can be seen in the example of citizens of countries such as Denmark, Finland, Norway, and Sweden. According to Hofstede, masculinity is an attribute of national culture that expresses the degree of social values characterized by assertiveness (confidence) and materialism. Femininity is an integral part of national culture and reflects the level of respect and consideration for others [5].

Strictly biological theories about the origin of gender roles, in particular evolutionary psychology, are not supported by empirical data. But it affects a wide range of human behavior. For example, a person's choice of clothing, profession, approach to things, personal relationships and how he or she behaves in these relationships are taken into account. In general, the available scientific data indicate that the development of gender is influenced not only by biological factors, but also by cognitive and social factors. Despite the broad understanding of the term "gender role", it traditionally limits women to the private sphere, and men to the public. Sometimes various groups, especially feminist movements, try to change those aspects of gender roles that they consider repressive and cruel. Currently, the task of isolating it into an independent scientific category is becoming relevant. Gender culture is a concept with a wide range of meanings. In all areas of a developing and progressing society, women, along with men, strive to keep up with the times. Today, women are not only busy with housework and raising children, but also try to "keep up with both the family and their favorite business." However, there are some of the most pressing development issues that become potential obstacles to gender equality, and achieving this equality, especially gender equality between men and women in society and in the family, is the most difficult task. This remains one of the most important issues.

In this regard, it is necessary to clarify the concept of gender culture. Gender culture is determined by sex, and sex, in turn, refers to the biological differences between women and men. These physiological differences are determined by nature and are universal, definite and, as a rule,

permanent. The biological, physical and genetic structure with which we are born is called biological sex.

Modern social sciences distinguish between the concepts of sex and gender. Traditionally, the former was used to describe the anatomical and physiological characteristics of a person, primarily as a man or a woman. A person's sex (i.e. biological characteristics) is considered to be the basis and main cause of psychological and social differences between women and men. As scientific research continued, it became clear that from a biological point of view, there are more similarities between men and women than differences. Many researchers even believe that the only clear and significant biological difference between women and men is their role in reproduction. Nowadays, it is clear that “traditional” gender differences in men, such as height, weight, muscle mass, and physical strength, are highly variable and less gender-specific than was traditionally believed. For example, women in North-West Europe are usually taller than men in South-East Asia. Diet and lifestyle significantly affect height and body weight, as well as physical strength, which in turn determines who – men or women – needs more nutrition, who needs more calories. Social views on the nutritional value of foods have a big impact. Which sports are suitable for which or not? Based on biological differences between boys and girls, society sets different norms, standards of behavior, and roles for them. The so-called gender roles help create a “female” and a “male” world.

In the world of men, boys are taught to be strong, active and intelligent; they are encouraged to become managers, occupy high-paying positions and dominate public life. In the world of women, girls are taught to be weaker, more emotional, submissive, more passive than boys and are limited to housework and unpaid work. Thus, two worlds are opposed, creating a hidden asymmetry, where one sex dominates the other.

Based on the above, gender can be understood as a social construct, a set of characteristics determined by the culture of a society that determine the social behavior of men and women and the relationships between them. Gender is formed through a certain system of socialization, division of labor, cultural norms, socially accepted roles and stereotypes. Gender is a means of understanding social processes.

The concept of gender culture is a complex concept that encompasses sexual identity, roles and expectations in a social and cultural context. It determines the spiritual and social roles of the sexes, how they relate to each other.

If we study and analyze its essence, we can come to the conclusion that gender identity is how a person understands and accepts his or her gender. He or she can identify as a man, a woman, or a representative of another gender, using comparative descriptions or biological characteristics. Sexual identity also determines a person's individual or collective roles, that is, it affects how a person finds his or her place in society and what his or her social role will be. Therefore, sexual identity is of great importance in social, cultural, and personal contexts,[6] norms are a set of gender roles and expectations established in a society and reflected in the interactions between people. For example, men and women are assigned different roles and responsibilities in society.

Men are often seen as strong and aggressive, while women are seen as kind and caring. These norms influence people's behavior, attitudes, and decision-making. Sexual norms in a society can change, and in our time there are movements towards gender equality and social justice. For this reason, norms are not just agreements, but dynamic and evolving understandings. These concepts are terms that describe the essence of gender culture.

Gender is created (constructed) by society as a social model of women and men, defining the place and role of women and men in society and its institutions (family, political structure, economy, culture and education, etc.). Gender systems vary across societies, but in every society these systems are asymmetrical: men and everything "masculine" (character traits, behavior, professions, etc.) are considered primary, important, and dominant. "Woman"/"female" is defined as something secondary, socially insignificant, and submissive. [7] The essence of gender construction is polarity and opposition. The gender system reflects asymmetrical cultural values and expectations placed on people based on their gender. Over time, in almost every society, socially defined characteristics have come to be assigned to two genders (labels), and one biological sex has been assigned social roles that are culturally considered secondary. It does not matter what these social roles are: they may differ from society to society, but what is attributed and prescribed to women is considered second-class (second-rate). Social norms change over time, but gender asymmetry persists. [8] Thus, it can be said that the gender system is a socially constructed system of inequality based on sex. Gender is thus one of the ways of social stratification of society, which, together with socio-demographic factors such as race, ethnicity, class and age, forms a system of social hierarchy. In general, the scientific knowledge accumulated to date shows that representatives of different sexes are similar in almost everything, although exceptions are very few and relatively insignificant. Despite this, gender differences are given much attention both in the scientific community and beyond. Participants in the scientific discussion of gender differences are divided into two main camps: supporters of biological determinism, who believe in a close connection between biological sex and gender, and supporters of social constructivism, who believe that gender differences are constructed by society. Representatives of different camps approach the issue of gender differences in fundamentally different ways. Biologically oriented researchers often do not ask about the existence of gender differences, but implicitly assume their existence and look for explanations for them. Social constructivists, in turn, study how ideas about gender differences are used to construct gender processes and social hierarchies in various social contexts [9].

REFERENCES

1. 1.O‘zbekiston Respublikasining Qonuni “Xotin-qizlar va erkaklar uchun teng huquq hamda imkoniyatlar kafolatlari to‘g‘risida” O‘RQ-562-son 02.09.2019
2. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Oliy Majlisi Senatining qarori “2030 yilgacha gender tengligiga erishish strategiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida»gi SQ-297-IV-son 28.05.2021
3. Гидденс А. Социология: краткое, но критическое введение. – Лондон: Макмиллан, 1982.
4. Здравомыслова Е. Социальная конструкция гендера и гендерная система в России/ Гендерное измерение социальной и политической активности в переходный период. Сборник научных статей. Выпуск 4. - Санкт-Петербург, 1996, С.5-11.
5. Hofstede G. Masculinity and Femininity: The taboo dimension of national cultures, 1998. SAGE Publications Inc. 238 p
6. Исаев Д. Д. Системный подход к проблеме гендерной идентичности // Педиатр. — 2012. — Т. 3, № 4. — С. 37-40

7. Ситникова В. В. Гендерология и гендерные исследования в социальной работе: учебное пособие // АмГУ- 2018, С.21
8. Ерохина Л. Д а и др. Гендерология и феминология: учебное пособие// М., 2009. – с. 382
9. Клецина И. С. От психологии пола — к гендерным исследованиям в психологии // Вопросы психологии 2003. № 1. С. 61–78.